

Photoelectrochemical studies on galvanostatically formed (CdHg)Se films

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Electrosynthesis of titanium supported (CdHg)Se films has been carried out under controlled galvanostatic conditions to investigate their photoelectroconvertibility. Photoaction spectral studies have been made for the determination of their band-gap. Ability of these preparations to withstand corrosion has also been investigated on the basis of polarization studies. (CdHg)Se films formed galvanostatically exhibit somewhat enhanced photoresponsiveness and substantially improved resistance towards electrochemical corrosion.

Production of cheap photovoltaic and photoelectrochemical cells is a constant preoccupation of semiconductor electrochemists¹. In spite of this, development of photoelectrochemical converters of practical interest has not yet become possible. Strategies devised to obtain semiconductor based systems for sustained and efficient photoelectrochemical conversion have not led to any spectacular advancement². Mixed metal chalcogenides, specially (CdHg)Se is currently considered attractive because of manipulability of its band gap to match adequately the solar spectral distribution. Photoelectroconvertibility of such systems obtained by electrochemical codeposition has been investigated by some workers³. The present work reports the preparation of titanium supported (CdHg)Se films under controlled galvanostatic conditions. These preparations have been examined for their photoresponsiveness, and characterized on the basis of photoaction spectral studies. Corrosion behaviour of the electrodeposits has also been investigated using polarization studies⁴.

Results and Discussion

A summary of experimental conditions under which (CdHg)Se preparations were carried out is given in Table I. Film thickness values were estimated using the relationship⁵,

$$F_T = \frac{it(E.W.)}{F d A} \quad (1)$$

where, i is the constant deposition current, t the deposition time, $(E.W.)$ the equivalent wt. of the electrodeposit, F the Faraday constant, A the area of the deposited film, and d the density of deposited material.

All preparations were carried out using a constant current of 0.1 mA (current density = 0.4 mA cm⁻²) for 5 min. These experimental conditions were found earlier to yield electrodeposits endowed with acceptable photoelectrochemical characteristics. It may also be noted that during galvanostatic depositions, the deposition potential declined

somewhat in all cases. A representative plot depicting such variation is shown in Fig. 1. The magnitude of deposition

Fig. 1. Attainment of equilibrium in case of a representative electrodeposit.

Fig. 2. Initial and final potentials during galvanostatic depositions when electroplating solutions having different concentrations are used (O) initial potential and (●) final potential

Fig. 3. Variation of photoactivity with concentration of HgCl₂. All solutions contain 0.01 M CdSO₄ + 0.001 M SeO₂ and variable concentration of HgCl₂. Galvanostatic deposition carried out using current 0.1 mA.

potential depends on the concentration of mercuric chloride in electroplating solutions used, which all contain 0.01 M CdSO₄ and 0.001 M SeO₂ (Fig. 2). These results indicate progressive simultaneous reduction of Hg²⁺ ions during electrochemical formation of (CdHg)Se. All (CdHg)Se preparations were tested for their photoactivity in 0.5 M CdSO₄ containing 0.1 M KI and 0.2 mM I₂ solutions. The photoelectroactivity of such preparations depends on the concentration of HgCl₂ (Fig. 3). Inclusion of Hg in the electrodeposit is shown later to be conducive to increased light absorbability because of lowering of the band gap.

Some of the electrodes showed deterioration in photoactivity upon being illuminated repeatedly (Table 2). The electrodes, however, when tested in 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ containing 0.1 M K₄Fe(CN)₆ and 0.01 M K₃Fe(CN)₆ exhibited reproducible photoactivity. The redox potential of I₂/I₃⁻ is +0.535 V while that of [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻/[Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ redox couple is +0.69 V. The semiconductor is therefore prone to enhanced electrochemical corrosion in the I₂/I₃⁻ redox couple as a result of which its photoelectroconvertibility is adversely affected.

Table 1. Summary of experimental conditions

Electroplating solution : 0.01 M CdSO₄ + 0.001 M SeO₂ + HgCl₂,
electrode area = 0.25 cm², deposition current = 0.1 mA, deposition time = 5 min

Preparation	Concn. of HgCl ₂ 10 ⁻⁵ M	Film thickness 10 ⁻⁴ cm
1	2	3.416
2	4	3.418
3	6	3.421
4	8	3.423
5	10	3.425
6	100	3.453

Fig. 4 A representative photoaction spectrum.

Fig. 5. E_p² vs λ plot for the estimation of band-gap.

Table 2. Photoactivity of preparation 6 in I_2/I_3^- and $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}/[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$ redox systems

Testing solution			Testing solution		
0.5 M CdSO ₄ + 0.1 M KI + 0.2 mM I ₂			20.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ + 0.1 M K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ + 0.01 M K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆		
E _D	E _L	E _P	E _D	E _L	E _P
mV	mV	mV	mV	mV	mV
+84	-119	-203	-3	-259	-256
+79	-98	-177	-6	-260	-254
+90	-85	-175	-4	-258	-254
+107	-38	-145	-5	-257	-252

For the purpose of determination of the effect of progressive inclusion of mercury in the electrodeposit, photoaction spectral measurements were carried out. Representative spectral data are included in Fig. 4. The band-gap values derived from E_p^2 vs λ plots (Fig. 5) are summarized in Table 3. These values are accurate upto ± 0.03 eV. A progressive reduction in the band-gap of (CdHg)Se with HgCl₂ concentrations in the electroplating solution is observed. These findings are in agreement with those reported earlier⁶ wherein electrodeposition was carried out under potentiostatic control.

Table 3. Summary of experimental results

Preparation	R _p	i _c	R _c	Band-gap eV
	10 ³ Ω	10 ⁻⁶ A	10 ⁻⁹ g s ⁻¹	
1	5.00	5.14	2.97	1.70
2	7.11	3.61	2.05	1.69
3	7.63	3.37	1.92	1.68
4	7.83	3.28	1.87	1.65
5	2.98	8.62	4.92	1.61
6	-	-	-	1.56

Inclusion of mercury is likely to alter corrosion characteristics of the (CdHg)Se electrodeposit. With a view to investigate this aspect of the (CdHg)Se behaviour, polarization measurement was carried out to estimate polarization resistance (R_p) using current-voltage data in the low field domain. The R_p values were used to estimate corrosion current (i_c) and the corrosion rate (R_c) using the relationships⁷,

$$i_c = \frac{RT}{F R_p} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } R_c = \frac{i_c (E.W.)}{F} \quad (3)$$

The R_p , i_c and R_c values derived on the basis of polarization studies for various (CdHg)Se electrodeposits are summarized in Table 3. It may be noted that the galvanostatically formed (CdHg)Se films exhibit substantially enhanced resistance towards corrosion in comparison to the electrodeposited films prepared under potentiostatic control⁶. Furthermore, a sharp reduction in corrosion resistance as well as photoactivity is observed when HgCl₂ concentration in the electroplating solution is 10 mM and above.

Experimental

For electrochemical synthesis of (CdHg)Se films using galvanostatic technique, titanium foils (Titanium Equipment and Anode Manufacturing Co. Ltd., Madras) were polished with diamond paste, Metsec Fluid (Madras Metallurgical Service Pvt. Ltd.) and washed successively with acetone and distilled water. A three-electrode system consisting of a titanium working electrode, a titanium counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used for electrodeposition. Passage of constant current was ensured using constant current power source (Lake Shore 120, USA). During galvanostatic deposition variation in the potential of the working electrode was monitored using SCE. Preparation of (CdHg)Se films was carried out using constant current density of 0.4 mA cm⁻² for 5 min time-intervals. CdSO₄ and HgCl₂ (both B.D.H.) and SeO₂ (Fluka) were used for the preparation of electroplating solutions. The depositions were tested for their photoresponsiveness in I_2/I_3^- redox-couple along with CdSO₄ supporting electrolyte, using 1 kW Tungsten lamp as a light-source. For photoaction spectral studies f/3.4 monochromator (Applied Photophysics) was used. Current-voltage behaviour of the galvanostatically formed (CdHg)Se electrodeposits was examined to obtain polarization curves using electrochemical impedance measurement system (Model 378, EG & G, PARC) consisting of Model 273 potentiostat/galvanostat in conjunction with an IBM compatible AT personal computer. Polarization resistance values were obtained from these data to estimate corrosion current.

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